

COMPARISON OF GROWTH AND YIELD POTENTIALS OF RED AND GREEN ROSELLE -*HIBISCUS SABDARIFFA* IN ALICE, EASTERN CAPE, SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

Hibiscus sabdariffa L. Roselle is a plant noted for its therapeutic functions especially against many chronic diseases. The plant is, however, not popularly consumed in South Africa despite its existing benefits. In this study, the growth and yield potentials of green and red cultivars of roselle were evaluated both in greenhouse and field in Alice, Eastern Cape, South Africa. The results showed that, red cultivars was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than green in growth attributes in both locations. Also, red roselle had higher number of calyces than green having the mean values of 3.9 ± 0.83 and 4.1 ± 0.83 in the greenhouse and 101.7 ± 23.29 and 149.8 ± 44.92 in the field for green and red cultivar respectively. Red roselle also had higher yield than green with total calyces yield of 156 and 176 kg/ha and 2,435 and 3,729kg/ha for green and red cultivars in greenhouse and field respectively. Although, red roselle had higher yield than green, both cultivars thrived in this study and can be cultivated profitably when sown in September in Alice. Production of roselle in this province add to the food base of people and reduce the prevalence of some diseases.

Keywords: *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, Roselle Cultivation, Growth and Yield, South Africa, Green and Red Roselle.

Introduction

Roselle is an annual or perennial plant, which is cultivated in warm temperate, tropical and sub-tropical regions for bast fiber, paper pulp or edible calyces, leaves or seeds (Osman *et al.*, 2011). It is a popular vegetable cultivated for its leaves, seeds stems and calyces with the dried calyces used to prepare tea, syrup, jams, jelly most importantly as beverages (Eslaminejad & Zakari, 2011). Both leaves and calyces are the plant parts consumed as food. The young leaves are consumed just like spinach with the leaves mixed with other vegetables and food condiment. Roselle is a major cash crop in China, Sudan and Thailand and a minor vegetable crop in several other tropical and sub-tropical countries around the world (Ramos *et al.*, 2011). It is a photoperiodic plant, which takes about six months to mature (Ansari *et al.*, 2013). Mahadevan *et al.*, (2009) reported that, in many

parts of the world, leaves are consumed as green vegetable; stem is used as a source of pulp for paper industry while calyces are used as coloring agent and for beverages. In addition to their uses, various parts of the plants have been used in the traditional medicines for the treatment of diseases (Salami & Afolayan, 2020). The plant is very popular for its medicinal functions (Eslaminejad *et al.*, 2012). Eastern Cape is the second most populous province in South Africa and is a region where majority of people are faced with problems of poverty, diseases and malnutrition. The temperature range within which the plant thrives is between 18 and 35°C with an optimum of 25°C, while growth of the plant ceases at 14°C (McClintock & Tahir, 2004). Annual rainfall range of 400 – 500 mm is necessary (Augstburger *et al.*, 2000). It thrives under full sun. Flowering of the plant is excellent when daylight was shorter than 12 hour, but

flowering does not occur, if there are more than 13 hours of sunlight in a day (Duke, 1983). Rudgers, (2018) affirmed that, roselle is relatively hardy and can survive in most soil types but best performed in sandy loam to loamy sand with pH from 5.5 – 6.8 Eastern Cape is among the areas that are suitable for roselle production in South Africa (African Rosella, 2011). The habitat of common Hibiscus species is mainly Limpopo, Mpumalanga, Kwa Zulu- Natal and Eastern province (African Rosella, 2011).

Despite these facts, Eastern Cape of South Africa has not given attention to roselle in spite of uses and availability of its wild species in the province. This valuable crop is strange to many people within the Province especially in Alice where many people could not recognize the plant not to talk of consuming, those farmers that knew the plant called it 'bush flower' admitting the plant's beauty. Alice is one of the towns in Eastern Cape, the climate zone according to Koppen classification belongs to cfa category (climate-Data.org.2018). It has humid subtropical climate, the climate is generally warm and temperate with average temperature and rainfall of 18.0°C and 574mm respectively. No dry month in summer (www.enwikipedia.org, 2018). Commercialization of roselle in this province will not only add to the food base of people, it will also create job, improve means of livelihood, and reduce the prevalence of some diseases as the plant is noted to be highly therapeutic on many chronic diseases. The essential oils and medicinal plants program, which is funded by South Africa Department of Science and Technology, seeks to put the cultivation of medicinal plants and the manufacture of herbal remedies on a sound commercial footing (Horak, 2008). This is an excellent opportunity for people to be well employed because of availability of arable land for production.

The demands of the majority in Africa for medicinal plants have been met by indiscriminate harvesting of spontaneous flora including those in the forests. As a result, many plant species have been extinct while some are already endangered. On the other hand, in some developing countries including South Africa, roselle has not been fully exploited despite the existing potentials for use and production. It is therefore necessary that, systematic cultivation of medicinal plants be introduced in order to conserve biodiversity and protect threatened species and in order to create awareness on the crop where it is underutilized such as South Africa for better utilization. Besides, little research in terms of cultivation, agronomy and production has been carried out on the plant (FAO). In addition, most researches focused red cultivar while the green type was ignored; the green cultivar is also needed to be explored for biodiversity improvement.

The aim of this study is to investigate and compare the growth and yield potentials of green and red roselle at both greenhouse and field in Alice, Eastern Cape Province, South Africa.

Materials and method

The study was carried out at University of Fort Hare in Alice in Eastern parts of South Africa. The annual temperature ranged between a minimum of 10.06; 10.82°C and a maximum of 24.4; 25.18 with relative humidity of 35.71; 36.4% and mean annual rainfall of about 46.60; 41.10 cm in the year 2017 and 2018 respectively. The meteorological data for the location during the 2017 and 2018 is presented in Table 1. Two experiments were conducted, one in greenhouse and one in the farm, each experiment was repeated after the main experiments.

Experiment 1- Greenhouse

The seeds were collected from Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T),

Ibadan Nigeria the identity of the seeds were confirmed by the herbarium of the Institute. The growth and yield performance of green and red roselle were investigated at the greenhouse from September 2017 to February, 2018 (During summer) (Figs.1-3). Pre-planting soil analysis was carried out. The seeds were first sown in the sowing trays, nursed for 4 weeks and transplanted into 10 Kg pots. The experiment was designed in a completely randomized design of two treatments and ten replicates. From each cultivar, a sample of 10 plants was randomly selected for data collection. Average temperature of the greenhouse was from 24.19 °C but rose to about 37°C at the last phase of the growth of the plants while the relative humidity was 63.5%. The following growth attributes were measured at interval of 14 days until full maturity:

Plant height, stem diameter, leaf number, and number of branches. Also leaf area was calculated the formula $0.48 + 0.58L^2$ (Nnebue, 2015)

At maturity: Calyces number / plant, calyces fresh weight (g)/plant and calyces dry weight (g) / plant were also determined (after harvesting) (Figs. 4 and 5).

Total yield of the calyces (kg/ha) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Total calyces yield} = \frac{\text{calyces yield (Kg)} \times 2,000,000}{10 \text{ Kg}}$$

The experiment was repeated from February to June 2018.

Experiment 2- Field

The study was conducted from September 2017 to February 2018. Seeds of green and red cultivars of roselle were sown in the sowing tray (in the greenhouse) and transplanted into different experimental beds at a spacing of 30 cm x 60 cm. Each experimental unit (bed) had dimension of 120 cm X 270 cm containing 30 plants. Five plants were randomly selected from

Table1. Pre-planting physical and chemical properties of soil in the greenhouse and farm.

each bed for data collection. The experimental beds for the two cultivars were laid out in a randomized complete block design and replicated twice. Four weeks after sowing data collection commenced and continued at interval of 14 days to measure the growth attributes as shown above.

At maturity, the following yield attributes were measured: Number of calyces/plant, weight of fresh calyces/plant and weight of dry calyces/plant

Total calyces yield (kg / ha) was also calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Total calyces yield} \left(\frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{Ha}} \right) = \frac{\text{calyces yield per plot (Kg)} \times 10000}{\text{Harvested plot area (m}^2\text{)}}$$

The experiment was repeated after the main experiment but not successful due to the effects of approaching winter.

Method of Data Analysis

The results of the experiments were expressed as Mean ± SD using the Microsoft excel 2010 spreadsheet. Data were subjected to statistical analysis using MINITAB Release 17. Means were separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) paired wise comparison. The means were treated as significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The result of pre-planting physical and chemical analysis of the soil indicates that the soil in the greenhouse was sandy clay loam while that of the field was sandy loam. The result showed that the soils were rich in Nitrogen, phosphorus, total cation and pH values were within the recommended level. The soils were thus suitable for good growth of roselle (Table 1).

Soil parameters	Greenhouse	Farm
Soil density mg/L	0.80	0.87
Nitrogen (%)	0.59	0.42
Organic Carbon (%)	>6	4.5
Available Phosphorus	140	150
Potassium mg/L	1626	1356
Calcium mg/L	4272	3039
Magnesium mg/L	976	642
Exchangeable acids Cmol/L	0.11	0.09
Total cation Cmol/L	33.62	24.01
Acid salt (%)	0	0
pH (KCL)	6.61	6.51
Zinc mg/L	27.5	31.1
Manganese mg/L	3	4
Cu mg/L	6.2	7.8
Sand (%)	57.5	56.0
Silt (%)	20	25.0
Clay (%)	22.5	19.0
Soil textural class	Sandy clay loam	Sandy loam

Table 2: Meteorological data of University of Fort Hare, Alice, Eastern Cape South Africa (September, 2017 to June, 2018)

Months	Ave Max Temp.(°C)		Ave Min Temp.s (°C)		Total Rain (mm)		Ave. Max Rel. hum (%)		Ave. Min. Rel. Hum. (%)	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
Jan	-----	29.13	-----	15.64	-----	54.86	-----	87.5	-----	23.13
Feb	-----	27.64	-----	15.19	-----	53.59	-----	90.25	-----	45.97
March	-----	24.47	-----	13.74	-----	57.4	-----	91.03	-----	51.19
April	-----	24.37	-----	10.84	-----	62.23	-----	90.41	-----	42.32
May	-----	23.72	-----	6.17	-----	14.47	-----	90.04	-----	30.13
June	-----	21.6	-----	3.31	-----	4.06	-----	86.67	-----	25.63
July	-----	---	-----	---	-----	---	-----	---	-----	---
August	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
September	22.98	-----	8.86	-----	23.11	-----	88.58	-----	37.16	-----
October	23.42	-----	8.9	-----	84.84	-----	88.43	-----	37.8	-----
November	24.2	-----	11.39	---	91.69	-----	88.93	-----	41.86	-----
December	24.99	---	13.05	-----	48.26	-----	88.73	-----	44.45	-----

Source: Alice weather summary University of Fort Hare, Alice, Eastern Cape, South Africa

3.1 Growth characteristics of red and green roselle.

Plant Height

The mean height for both cultivars varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) in all the experiments where red roselle height was observed to be higher than green. At 20 weeks after sowing (WAS), harvesting was carried out for the first greenhouse experiments (in summer) while at 16

WAS harvesting was done for the second greenhouse experiment due to approach of winter. Roselle attained the mean height of 68.99cm; 88.04cm, 113.35cm; 129.0cm and 30.55; 41.08 cm for green and red in greenhouse (during summer), field (summer) and greenhouse during autumn respectively. (Tables 3- 5).

Stem Diameter

ANOVA result on stem diameter showed that, in the first greenhouse experiment, stem diameter for both roselle was statistically at par at the initial growth stage. At 10 WAS red roselle was significantly wider than green until harvest time when 2.75 cm and 2.98 cm were recorded for stem diameter of green and red respectively (Tables 3-5). On the field, no variation occurred at the initial growth stage but at 10 WAS red stem became thicker significantly, and later equalized with green at 14 WAS until harvesting time when green cultivar was 3.33 and red 5.53 cm wide. For the second greenhouse experiment, stem diameter took the same trend and had values of 0.52 and 0.59 for green and red roselle respectively at harvesting time (Tables 3- 5).

Number of Leaves

The result showed that apart from 6 and 10 WAS, leaf number for red was significantly higher than that of green until the harvest time when 80.10 and 131.60 were recorded for green and red respectively. On the field also green roselle leaf number was significantly higher than red at 4 and 6 WAS, the values then equalized and later became significantly higher than green until harvest time when 273.20 and 378.30 for green and red were recorded respectively. Similarly, the result of the second greenhouse experiment showed that there was no significant variation in the leaf number of the two cultivars; however, from 10WAS until harvest time, red cultivars became higher significantly than green (Tables 3-5).

Number of Branches

In the first greenhouse experiment, ANOVA result showed that except at 10 – 14 WAS when number of branches for red roselle was not successful because of incoming winter.

significantly higher than green, no significant variation was observed from the initial growth period to harvest time when 20.50 was recorded as the mean branch number for the two types. However, on the farm, red type was significantly higher at the initial and mid growth period and later equalized until harvest time when 21.22 and 22.90 mean branch number for green and red was recorded. In addition, for the second greenhouse experiment, red roselle significantly had more branches than green at most period of growth until harvest time when the mean branch numbers were 3.10 and 3.50 for green and red respectively (Tables 3-5).

Leaf Area

The result of the first greenhouse experiment showed that, red cultivar significantly had bigger leaves than green at the initial growth period. At 8WAS however, the values were at par and later became higher than green and equalized at harvest time when 101 cm², 52 cm², 103 cm², 34 cm² were recorded for green and red respectively. On the field, there was no significant difference between the cultivars at early and mid-growth periods. At 12WAS, however, red became significantly higher than green until harvest time when 96.49 cm² and 121.85 cm² were recorded for green and red respectively. At the second greenhouse experiment, no significant difference was observed at the initial stage, red later became higher as the growth progressed but higher leaf area was observed for green at the harvest time when 37.65 cm² and 24.81 cm² were recorded for green and red respectively (Tables 3-5). It is noteworthy that, first greenhouse plants did not flower; the experiment was terminated at six months. In addition, the second trial on the farm

Table 3. Growth characteristics of green and red roselle from September 2017 to March 2018 - greenhouse

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Number of leaves	Number of branches	Leaf area (cm ²)
4WAS Green	12.42 ± 1.47 ^b	0.29 ± 0.04 ^a	8.10 ± 1.64 ^b	4.60 ± 0.49 ^a	20.69 ± 7.62 ^b

	Red	15.38 ± 0.93 ^a	0.36 ± 0.05 ^a	9.60 ± 2.29 ^a	5.40 ± 0.80 ^a	24.51 ± 5.07 ^a
6WAS	Green	20.34 ± 3.17 ^b	2.09 ± 0.16 ^a	30.20 ± 9.21 ^a	9.00 ± 1.90 ^a	31.09 ± 12.92 ^b
	Red	25.69 ± 3.40 ^a	2.33 ± 0.19 ^a	31.60 ± 5.75 ^a	10.40 ± 1.43 ^a	35.06 ± 5.07 ^a
8WAS	Green	36.24 ± 8.26 ^b	2.51 ± 0.22 ^a	45.50 ± 11.05 ^b	11.00 ± 2.14 ^a	56.80 ± 23.60 ^a
	Red	48.64 ± 4.11 ^a	2.61 ± 0.22 ^a	53.20 ± 7.63 ^a	12.00 ± 2.79 ^a	50.63 ± 12.65 ^b
10WAS	Green	46.78 ± 8.24 ^b	2.46 ± 0.21 ^b	77.70 ± 14.77 ^a	14.30 ± 2.15 ^b	100.09 ± 41.12 ^a
	Red	52.42 ± 16.5 ^a	2.69 ± 0.13 ^a	76.30 ± 12.35 ^a	15.60 ± 2.29 ^a	119.20 ± 57.00 ^a
12WAS	Green	56.54 ± 14.35 ^b	2.57 ± 0.14 ^b	95.50 ± 49.72 ^b	15.30 ± 2.05 ^b	102.52 ± 19.09 ^a
	Red	77.25 ± 5.82 ^a	2.77 ± 0.09 ^a	143.30 ± 23.51 ^a	17.10 ± 1.37 ^a	122.79 ± 34.08 ^a
14WAS	Green	57.34 ± 9.43 ^b	2.60 ± 0.14 ^b	75.60 ± 13.09 ^b	17.30 ± 2.57 ^b	100.35 ± 38.94 ^a
	Red	74.88 ± 8.59 ^a	2.77 ± 0.08 ^a	112.90 ± 42.95 ^a	19.10 ± 1.87 ^a	115.69 ± 27.46 ^a
16WAS	Green	65.75 ± 9.48 ^b	2.67 ± 0.21 ^b	80.70 ± 12.12 ^b	19.10 ± 1.70 ^a	186.07 ± 93.02 ^b
	Red	84.19 ± 8.60 ^a	2.83 ± 0.05 ^a	133.50 ± 30.79 ^a	19.80 ± 1.60 ^a	212.11 ± 63.46 ^a
18WAS	Green	68.46 ± 9.81 ^b	2.72 ± 0.22 ^b	83.60 ± 9.80 ^b	19.80 ± 1.60 ^a	116.58 ± 14.53 ^b
	Red	87.31 ± 9.25 ^a	2.97 ± 0.10 ^a	138.80 ± 41.83 ^a	20.20 ± 1.33 ^a	145.23 ± 34.26 ^a
20WAS	Green	68.99 ± 9.73 ^b	2.75 ± 0.20 ^b	80.10 ± 8.31 ^b	20.50 ± 1.36 ^a	103.34 ± 41.3 ^a
	Red	88.04 ± 9.26 ^a	2.98 ± 0.09 ^a	131.60 ± 39.88 ^a	20.50 ± 1.36 ^a	101.52 ± 13.15 ^a

Values shown are mean ± SD; Means with the same letters are not significantly different P<0.05 WAS = Weeks after Sowing.

Table 4. Growth characteristics of green and red roselle on the field from September 2017 to March 2018

	Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Number of leaves	Number of branches	Leaf area (cm ²)
4WAS	Red	10.44 ± 1.13 ^a	0.17 ± 0.04 ^a	8.70 ± 2.93 ^b	1.20 ± 1.47 ^b	14.83 ± 4.10 ^a
	Green	11.58 ± 0.95 ^a	0.23 ± 0.01 ^a	13.40 ± 1.74 ^a	4.30 ± 0.46 ^a	14.60 ± 3.49 ^a
6WAS	Red	12.46 ± 1.16 ^b	0.20 ± 0.03 ^a	9.70 ± 2.83 ^b	3.30 ± 1.42 ^b	20.40 ± 4.73 ^a
	Green	16.95 ± 0.74 ^a	0.25 ± 0.01 ^a	15.90 ± 1.37 ^a	6.00 ± 0.77 ^a	17.83 ± 5.27 ^b
8WAS	Red	15.02 ± 1.80 ^b	0.47 ± 0.03 ^a	22.50 ± 1.86 ^a	8.10 ± 0.83 ^a	26.67 ± 5.47 ^a
	Green	17.89 ± 0.82 ^a	0.51 ± 0.04 ^a	25.7 ± 1.85 ^a	8.80 ± 0.75 ^a	26.15 ± 7.17 ^a
10WAS	Red	34.02 ± 2.66 ^a	1.26 ± 0.06 ^a	53.8 ± 3.76 ^a	14.20 ± 0.75 ^a	33.66 ± 5.95 ^a
	Green	34.55 ± 3.50 ^a	1.11 ± 0.01 ^b	42.40 ± 2.29 ^b	11.80 ± 0.75 ^b	30.95 ± 11.92 ^a
12WAS	Red	67.68 ± 5.81 ^a	1.43 ± 0.08 ^a	94.70 ± 4.29 ^a	14.10 ± 0.83 ^a	81.10 ± 7.22 ^a
	Green	56.80 ± 3.18 ^b	1.16 ± 0.03 ^b	87.10 ± 3.51 ^a	12.80 ± 0.75 ^a	69.17 ± 3.81 ^b
14WAS	Red	107.50 ± 7.24 ^a	1.97 ± 0.05 ^a	134.50 ± 3.91 ^a	14.80 ± 0.75 ^a	99.52 ± 6.72 ^a
	Green	80.36 ± 3.38 ^b	1.84 ± 0.09 ^a	114.20 ± 5.17 ^b	13.20 ± 0.75 ^a	75.56 ± 14.66 ^b
16WAS	Red	127.24 ± 5.99 ^a	2.77 ± 0.30 ^a	218.30 ± 4.88 ^b	20.80 ± 0.75 ^a	137.00 ± 16.97 ^a
	Green	110.66 ± 2.65 ^b	2.47 ± 0.03 ^a	185.20 ± 10.14 ^a	19.40 ± 1.11 ^a	100.99 ± 6.81 ^b
18WAS	Red	128.29 ± 5.74 ^a	3.49 ± 0.09 ^a	404.50 ± 26.89 ^a	21.60 ± 0.66 ^a	137.44 ± 24.15 ^a
	Green	112.60 ± 3.20 ^b	3.22 ± 0.05 ^a	285.80 ± 30.24 ^b	20.20 ± 0.87 ^a	111.86 ± 5.71 ^b
20WAS	Red	129.01 ± 5.74 ^a	3.53 ± 0.07 ^a	378.30 ± 80.51 ^a	22.70 ± 1.00 ^a	121.85 ± 24.73 ^a
	Green	113.35 ± 2.88 ^b	3.33 ± 0.08 ^a	273.20 ± 66.56 ^b	21.22 ± 1.13 ^a	96.49 ± 21.46 ^b

Table 5. Growth characteristics of green and red roselle in the greenhouse from February to June 2018

	Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Number of leaves	Number of branches	Leaf area (cm ²)
4WAS	Green	8.47 ± 1.27 ^b	0.24 ± 0.02 ^a	3.60 ± 0.92 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	8.31 ± 3.74 ^a
	Red	10.59 ± 1.52 ^a	0.27 ± 0.04 ^a	4.10 ± 0.54 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	8.08 ± 4.00 ^a
6WAS	Green	12.54 ± 3.12 ^b	0.29 ± 0.02 ^a	4.50 ± 0.92 ^a	0.90 ± 0.54 ^b	11.95 ± 4.49 ^b

	Red	17.58 ± 1.76 ^a	0.31 ± 0.03 ^a	5.70 ± 0.64 ^a	1.10 ± 0.30 ^a	16.17 ± 5.17 ^a
8WAS	Green	15.23 ± 3.51 ^b	0.25 ± 0.06 ^b	5.90 ± 1.37 ^a	1.90 ± 0.30 ^b	16.78 ± 8.20 ^b
	Red	24.38 ± 3.04 ^a	0.35 ± 0.07 ^a	7.60 ± 0.80 ^a	2.30 ± 0.46 ^a	34.98 ± 6.79 ^a
10WAS	Green	18.96 ± 6.83 ^b	0.34 ± 0.16 ^b	6.30 ± 2.65 ^b	2.40 ± 0.80 ^a	20.64 ± 12.66 ^a
	Red	27.76 ± 8.59 ^a	0.43 ± 0.16 ^a	8.60 ± 3.10 ^a	2.60 ± 0.92 ^a	25.80 ± 14.11 ^a
12WAS	Green	24.01 ± 9.91 ^b	0.45 ± 0.13 ^a	7.53 ± 2.82 ^b	2.60 ± 0.49 ^b	20.92 ± 11.08 ^b
	Red	38.73 ± 6.53 ^a	0.58 ± 0.07 ^b	10.00 ± 2.75 ^a	3.20 ± 0.87 ^a	29.28 ± 16.63 ^a
14WAS	Green	23.83 ± 9.54 ^b	0.46 ± 0.16 ^a	8.10 ± 3.33 ^b	2.70 ± 0.64 ^b	26.94 ± 13.38 ^b
	Red	41.20 ± 7.20 ^a	0.57 ± 0.09 ^a	11.60 ± 3.04 ^a	3.90 ± 0.70 ^a	46.09 ± 8.92 ^a
16WAS	Green	30.85 ± 9.06 ^b	0.52 ± 0.13 ^a	8.20 ± 2.14 ^b	3.10 ± 0.70 ^b	37.68 ± 8.89 ^a
	Red	41.08 ± 8.65 ^a	0.59 ± 0.08 ^a	10.10 ± 3.27 ^a	3.50 ± 0.92 ^a	24.81 ± 13.45 ^b

Means with the same letters are not significantly different P<0.05 WAS = Weeks after Sowing.

Yield Characteristics of Red and Green Roselle

Number of calyces in red in the first greenhouse was significantly higher than green having mean calyces number of 3.9 and 4.1 for green and red. Similarly on the field, red calyces was significantly higher than green having 149.8 and

101.7 mean calyx number. The fresh and dry weights took the same trend, red being higher than green in weight. Total yield (kg/ha) at green house was 158 kg/ha and 176 kg/ha for green and red. Similarly in the farm, the total yield were 2,435 and 3,729 kg/ha for green and red respectively (Table 6).

Table 6: Yield characteristics of green and red roselle

Treatments	Greenhouse		Farm	
	Green	Red	Green	Red
Mean calyces no.	3.9±0.83 ^b	4.1±0.83 ^a	101.7±23.29 ^b	149.8±44.92 ^a
Calyces mean fresh wt.	7.93±1.33 ^b	9.70±1.86 ^a	284.39±77.91 ^b	427.87±144.16 ^a
Calyces mean dry wt.	0.79±0.14 ^a	0.88±0.20 ^a	26.30±6.73 ^b	40.28±14.35 ^a
Total yield kg/ha	158 ^b	176 ^a	2,435 ^b	3,729 ^a

Means with the same letters are not significantly different P<0.05

Figure 1: A= Red roselle in the first greenhouse experiment; B= Green roselle in the first greenhouse experiment.

Figure 4: A= Green roselle; B= Fruits; C= Calyces and and fruit pods; D= Seeds and dry calyces.

Figure 5: A= Red roselle; B= Fruits; C= Fruit pods and Calyces; D= Dry calyces and seeds.

Discussion

The result of current study revealed that, red cultivar of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* has higher growth rate and yield than green cultivar when cultivated in the greenhouse or on the field. All the growth attributes from the three experiments showed that, red roselle had higher growth potentials than green; this was also reflected on the yield. Cheng (2004) found that, roselle plants with a high mean stem were stronger and more productive compared to short plants. The result on stem diameter confirm the report of Osman & Islam, (2011) that stem diameter of red was wider than other accessions. Also, Arivazhagan & Manivanna, (2010) reported values more than 13 primary branches per roselle plant. The higher potential of red than green may likely be due to genetic differences. The yield values obtained in this study was lower than the value reported for roselle by McClintock & Tahir (2004).

Leaf area has been assumed to be closely related to leaf dry weight and plant total dry weight, hence, it can be estimated from the parameter (Chanda & Singh, 2002; Karimi *et al.*, 2008). Red type had bigger leaf area. Worthy of note is that the second greenhouse experiment the number of branches for green was more than that of red this may be due to physiological disturbances that the plant experienced from incoming winter. The effects were reflected on both growth and yield of the plants. This informed earlier harvesting (16WAS) than other two experiments. This really confirmed that roselle could not be grown in winter because the outside climatic condition had impact on greenhouse conditions. This supports the findings of Molton, (1987) and McClintock & Tahir, (2004) that, roselle cannot be cultivated throughout the year unlike kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.)

The greenhouse plants, which did not flower, may be because of high heat that the plants exposed to (around 38°C). At this time, the Alice sunlight intensity and temperature were very high, the outside temperature had influence in the

greenhouse temperature and this may affect the flowering. In addition, the high temperature with adequate water supply for the plants in the greenhouse pre-disposed the plants to fungal attack. This further reduced the vigor of the plants for flowering. Nnebue *et al.*, (2014) encountered the same problem in Owerri, Nigeria where roselle plants did not flower due to fungal attack occasioned by high temperature.

Although in most parts of the world, roselle is sown in July for the bloom to set in October and harvest November/ December, this could not work in Alice South Africa where the peak of the winter is July every year. Hence, the best growing period for roselle in Alice is from September (after winter) to March (before the next winter). The result of this study therefore is not in agreement with Christman (2003) who reported that, no matter when you sow, roselle will not bloom until days begin to shorten in October. Each part of the world has its own peculiarity.

Conclusion

Red roselle had higher growth and yield potentials than green when cultivated in the same environment. Unlike kenaf, green and red roselle cannot be cultivated in Alice throughout the year because they cannot survive very cold conditions (frost) especially from April to August. Although, red cultivar had higher growth and yield potential than green, green roselle also thrived in Alice, therefore both cultivars should be considered for cultivation for subsequent integration into the diet of people. If roselle is embraced for food and cultivated, it will not only serve as food medicine, but also create employment and improve the plant biodiversity in the area. In addition, roselle intended for leaves as vegetables may be sown in the greenhouse in September and harvested 10 weeks after sowing to avoid possible fungal infection when temperature becomes higher.

Roselle grown for calyces should however, be sown in September or early October and harvested latest March for good growth and yield.

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